

Enhancing Courtyard Spaces in Architecture Student Housing: Analysing the Factors Influencing Usage Efficiency

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Abstract

In today's technology-driven world, college students often find themselves immersed in redundant distractions, neglecting the potential benefits of spending time with nature. This paper proposes a solution to this issue by investigating of underutilized courtyard spaces in student housing which can be a versatile area for recreational activities. Specifically focusing on architecture student housing, this study investigates the efficiency of courtyards and the perceptual factors that influence their usage. Through the benchmarking method, the existing courtyards of student housing are analyzed to understand their current usage patterns. Furthermore, individual interviews are conducted with students who are residents of a National level architecture school in Vijayawada to gain insights into their perspectives on the existing courtyard and their views on efficient usage.

The findings reveal that local students highly value functional and aesthetic courtyard elements, emphasizing the significance of privacy and comfort for promoting efficient usage. By identifying these influencing factors, this study contributes to the development of a more student-centric approach to courtyard design in architecture student housing, fostering a greater connection between students and nature for enhanced well-being and academic performance.

Keywords: Courtyard; Efficient usage; Social interaction; Student housing; Utilization

Introduction

A courtyard of student housing serves as a flexible space that meets the inhabitants' functional and recreational needs. This versatile space, with natural elements such as lush foliage, trees, and water features, along with sunlight, transcends everyday aesthetics; it is a place of refuge. However, as a result of the changing dynamics of contemporary education and lifestyle, the optimal use of these courtyards is gradually diminishing. The once-vibrant courtyard is vanishing from the daily lives of students, potentially depriving them of its numerous benefits. Intriguingly, a courtyard can be referred to as a microcosm, as it encompasses the various lifestyles and preferences of its users. Classified into variants such as the single-line type, double-line type, L-type, and U-type courtyard (Lee & Park, 2015), A courtyard of student housing serves as a resilient space that meets the inhabitants' functional and recreational needs. As children mature into adults, they cultivate pastimes and routines that are shaped and molded by their values, beliefs, and perceptions. These behaviors are the result

of the user's desires, and when that passion is directed towards outdoor recreation, these pursuits provide the participant with potential benefits that may become apparent over time. (Mehlhaf, J. 2019)

Creating a nurturing environment near a student's living quarters can

have a significant impact on their way of life. As an extension of their personal space, the courtyard must be meticulously designed to entice its inhabitants. It must emanate a quality that entices students and effortlessly draws them into its embrace. It should reflect the preferences of the students by providing spaces for recreation, sports, and leisurely conversations. Courtyards with elements that promote happiness, nurture sportsmanship, and foster sociability. The combination of aesthetic appeal and the promise of enjoyment transforms the courtyard into a symphony of form and function. However, the aesthetic appeal is only the beginning of an evaluation that goes beyond the visual domain. The efficient use of courtyards in student accommodation involves considerably more than the physical arrangement of spaces. It encompasses the holistic well-being of young minds contending with newly acquired independence and academic challenges. These spaces, which can foster physical, social, and emotional development, must be fostered in kind. By harmonizing design with the changing preferences of the student population, we can not only reverse the trend of declining courtyard usage but also foster a renaissance of outdoor engagement. The courtyard, once restored to its central role, has the potential to rekindle connections – not only with the environment but also among students – reshaping the college experience and beyond. The

factors that contribute to the efficient usage of the

1. Literature Review

The incorporation and efficient utilization of open spaces, particularly courtyards, within student housing complexes is a crucial study for this rapidly urbanizing world. In an open space, the user needs physical and spatial aspects including maintenance, accessibility, safety, functionality, and availability of amenities (Abbasi, A., Alalouch, C., & Bramley, G. 2016). The courtyard spaces have the potential to cultivate social interactions, well-being, and a sense of connection with nature among university students, in addition to enhancing the physical environment. By delving into existing literature and combining it with germane insights, it is possible to identify the numerous benefits of incorporating open spaces into student housing designs. The study conducted on private housing developments constitutes an important investigation into the utilization of open

courtyard are further assessed.

spaces in the context of student housing. The motivation behind developers' provision of open spaces is frequently to facilitate social activities and interactions between residents. This study reveals, however, that maintenance plays a crucial role in sustaining residents' interest in utilizing these spaces (Anggiani, M., & Jamila, R. F. 2019). This highlights the significance of not only designing open spaces but also assuring their ongoing maintenance, to produce environments that are not only aesthetically pleasing but also functional and inviting. Open spaces within student housing complexes can have a significant impact on the well-being and quality of life of university students. The presence of well-designed and well-maintained open spaces in a student's living environment can provide a sanctuary where they can relax, recharge, and seek solace during their academic voyage.

Fig.1: Understanding the connection through the above diagram

Furthermore, the biophilia theory, which asserts that humans have an inherent affinity for nature, emphasizes the significance of incorporating natural elements into built environments (W.Browning, C. J. 2014) As a form of open space, courtyards can facilitate this essential connection with nature. Even within the confines of an urban campus, these courtyards can serve as tranquil retreats where students can immerse themselves in a natural environment. Including vegetation, water features, and elements that invoke a sense of nature can elicit positive emotional responses and contribute to the well-being of students as a whole. A study elaborate that students prefer more softscape than hardscape with more openness. Waterscapes and vegetative courtyards acts as a restorative factor than other landscapes. (Lu, M., & Fu, J. 2019)

In addition, these spaces can promote outdoor activities, exercise, and socialization, thereby fostering a holistic living experience that nourishes the mind and body. The importance of open spaces in nurturing social cohesion cannot be

overstated in a broader societal context. Student housing environments are microcosms of disparate cultures and backgrounds, making the design of spaces that promote interaction and comprehension of the utmost importance. Students can engage in impromptu interactions, collaborative study sessions, and cultural exchanges in courtyards due to their inherent potential as gathering locations. These interactions not only enhance the social lives of the students but also contribute to their personal development and global perspectives. Student housing open space utilization efficiency necessitates a comprehensive strategy addressing design, functionality, maintenance, and adaptability. To optimize the user experience, seating areas, pathways, and vegetation should be strategically placed. Moreover, design flexibility can accommodate the changing requirements of students, allowing the space to adapt to a variety of activities, from group gatherings to solitary reflection. The strategic utilization of open spaces, especially courtyards, in student accommodation has the

potential to significantly improve the lives of university students on multiple fronts. From fostering social interactions to promoting well-being and facilitating a connection with nature, these spaces transcend their tangible characteristics to become integral components of the student experience. The interaction between design, maintenance, and the intrinsic human affinity for nature renders these spaces not only architectural

elements but also catalysts for holistic community growth. As institutions continue to prioritize the success and well-being of their students, the incorporation of efficient open spaces exemplifies their dedication to creating hospitable and vibrant living environments. Factors that encourage the user to use an outdoor space are aesthetics, comfort, accessibility, connection with nature, activities, and privacy.

No.	Perceptual factors	Definitions
1	Aesthetic	The feeling of joy and pleasure experienced while viewing scenes of nature
2	Comfort	A peaceful and comfortable setting with well-kept landscaping, including paving, lighting, etc.
3	Accessibility	Easy to reach from the dwelling area, no barriers in time or space
4	Connection with nature	The environment is close to nature with pleasant view and sounds
5	Functional	The shared space that is utilized by the inhabitants for the purpose of recreation and social interaction
6	Privacy	A open to sky space which maintenance the privacy through good landscape
Table no.1: Factors that entice a user to utilize an outdoor space		

2. Materials And Methods

a. Data collection

The research for efficient usage of the courtyard and its factors is analyzed through Quantitative (benchmarking methodology) and qualitative (perceptual factors) Analysis. Initially, the primary and secondary data are collected. The primary data includes the documentation of the courtyards in the Girl's hostel of the National Institute, School of Planning and Architecture, Vijayawada. Due to time constraints, female students tend to spend leisure time within the student housing, as a result, the research was conducted there, followed by calculating the number and area of all the courtyards, their frequency of usage, factors that make the user to use the courtyard. Furthermore, a survey of users' perceptions was conducted and suggestions for efficient usage of the courtyards were collected from the inmates of the girls hostel. The secondary data includes studying various parameters, those that affect and influence the usage of an open space which includes functionality, aesthetics, comfort, accessibility, privacy, and connection with nature. These parameters are further studied in context with the student housing of the national institute.

b. Quantitative analysis

The rate of utilization is to be bench-marked, it is further calculated through the Space utilization rate formula in which Frequency is obtained based on the hours the students use the courtyard by the hours available and the Occupancy is the total number of students allocated to each courtyard by function of the total capacity of the particular courtyard and

hours used., and the Utilization is a function of frequency and occupancy.

$$\text{Frequency}(F) = (\text{Hours used} / \text{Hours available}) \times 100$$

$$\text{Occupancy}(O) = (\text{Total students} / \text{Capacity} \times \text{Hours used}) \times 100$$

$$*(\text{total students} = \text{total students inhabit around the courtyard})$$

$$\text{Utilization}(U) = (\text{Frequency} \times \text{Occupancy}) / 100$$

c. Qualitative analysis:

The perceptual factors for the efficient usage of the courtyard are derived from the secondary data. An outdoor space in student housing is used for restoration, socialization, and other functional purposes. The factors taken into account for analyzing the utilization are aesthetics, Comfort, accessibility, connection with nature, functionality, privacy.

d. Questionnaires design

The questionnaire was prepared to understand (1) students' perceptions of the existing courtyard, (2) features in the courtyard they perceive would make them go out more often, (3) the Preferred size and shape of the courtyard (4) frequency and hours of usage.

The target population was the female students of Architecture college who were dwelling around the courtyards. Before conducting the questionnaire survey, a pilot survey is done with a small sample of the target population.

The survey is done separately for the three categories of courtyard Small courtyard(Sc), Medium courtyard(MC), and Large courtyard(LC) to understand its effect on the utilization. The image and numbers of courtyard are given below:

Fig.2: Small courtyards in female student housing, SPAV

Fig.3: Medium courtyards in female student housing, SPAV

Fig.4: Large courtyards in female student housing, SPAV

Fig.5: Plan of Student housing for girls SPA, Vijayawada, Andhra Pradesh

Findings and Discussions

Data collection:

The housing units at the National Institute School of Planning and Architecture, Vijayawada have interconnected courtyards. The housing unit taken for study has 13 courtyards with varying sizes as a

Based on the survey it was found that the female students of the housing unit primarily preferred using the smaller and medium-sized courtyards for easy accessibility and functionality. The percentage of hardscape and softscape used for accessibility are as follows: 1) Small courtyard - 90% softscape & 10% hardscape 2) Medium courtyard - 45% softscape & 55% hardscape 3) Large courtyard - 80% softscape & 20% hardscape Among the total 363 users in the

result they were categorized into small, medium, and large size courtyards for further study. Small courtyards (Sc) were numbered 4, 7, 10 & 11 (20.25 sqm. to 29 sqm.); Medium courtyards (MC) were numbered as 1, 3, 5, 6, 8, 13 (30sqm. to 50sqm.); Large courtyard(LC) were numbered as 2, 9, 12 (51sqm. to 72 sqm.)

student housing units, around 25- 30 users are inhabiting each courtyard. The capacity of the courtyard is derived based on the total number of rooms around the courtyard. Taking into consideration the college hours and the time required for other basic needs, the average duration that the female students used the courtyards was around 8 hours a day (available hours).

sr.no	Courtyard type	Size no.(sq.m)	Courtyards	Landscape elements
1	Large courtyard (LC)	20.25 - 29	4,7,10,11	Small courtyard - 90% softscape & 10% hardscape
2	Medium courtyard (MC)	30 - 50	1.3.5.6.8.13	Medium courtyard - 45% softscape & 55% hardscape
3	Small courtyard (SC)	51 - 72	2,9,12	Large courtyard - 80% softscape & 20% hardscape

Table no.2: Types and specifications of courtyards in SPAV

a. Quantitative analysis:

The survey was conducted in a female housing unit of the national institute (sample number=130). According to the survey conducted the period of usage of the courtyard per student per day is a aximum of 45mins (0.75 hr) in the case of a small courtyard; 40mins (0.67 hr) in the case of medium size courtyard; 15mins (0.25 hr) in the case of large size courtyard. .Based on the results of the survey it was seen that the female students preferred smaller

courtyard number 4 the most, followed by courtyard number 7 and 13.

Courtyard numbers 4 and 7 are SC and the privacy it provides proved to be a decisive factor for the preference by the female students. Whereas courtyard number 13 is a MC due to the presence of medium dense vegetation, the degree of enclosure is increased hence providing privacy.

Fig.6: Graph showing the Courtyard of user preference

Fig.7: Graph showing the F,O & U of each courtyard

Qualitative analysis:

The courtyard students prefer has Shade(comfort), privacy, functionality, accessibility, and aesthetics and is more connected with nature. The major factor that influences efficient usage from the user's perception is accessibility, functionality, and connection with nature. Seaters and Socializing space is most needed in the courtyard from the user's perspective. Seating space for social interactions can be given as individual as well as combined space as 35.1% of users like spending time with others and 49.1% like spending some time alone with nature.

Conclusion

The primary objective of this research was to assess the effective utilization of courtyards within a residential complex designed for architectural students. Additionally, the study aimed to highlight the key determinants influencing the utilization patterns. By promoting outdoor engagement among students, the study sought to enhance their overall living experience. The methodology employed for this investigation centered around a benchmarking approach, enabling a thorough evaluation of usage efficiency. By aligning existing research outcomes with user perceptions, the study aimed to discern the pivotal factors influencing courtyard utilization. To gain valuable insights into the most influential factors driving efficient usage, a survey coupled with observational analysis was conducted. Pre-existing literature and past research indicated that larger courtyards with extensive open spaces would encourage user engagement and well-being. However, the outcomes of the survey presented a contrasting viewpoint. Contrary to expectations,

respondents exhibited a preference for courtyards with a smaller footprint. This preference was primarily attributed to a blend of privacy and functionality, with participants valuing these aspects over others. This research underscores the dynamic interplay between landscape design, user preferences, and practical considerations. It elucidates the user-driven inclination toward smaller courtyards that offer a harmonious blend of personal space and functional utility. This stands in contrast to the conventional notion that larger, more expansive layouts are inherently superior. These findings hold implications, particularly in the context of housing for female architecture students. Furthermore, it's important to note that these results could vary based on gender and specific requirements, which could be explored in more depth in future research.

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